

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich structures are a most promising type of construction where a weak, low-density core supports thin layers of high strength face materials. Most of the theories used for the analysis of such structures apply Mindlin assumptions, usually through a homogenization procedure. In this paper, a more accurate model is proposed. Each layer of a three-layer laminate can rotate independently, due to its material characteristics. Mindlin kinematic relations are then imposed in each layer. In the displacement-based finite-element model, each node possesses 9 degrees of freedom, with displacement continuity imposed at the interfaces. The transverse shear stresses are accurately computed, at each layer mid-surface. In the present model, transverse shear correction factors are not necessary. The numerical example discussed shows good performance of the element in sandwich plate situations.

Keywords: Sandwich structures, finite-element analysis, plates, composites, local rotations

1. INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are one of the most successful areas of research and development in composite materials field. The literature in this field is relatively large. Allen [1] published theories for sandwich plate analysis. Pagano [2],[3] presented exact solutions for simple cases, considering the transverse shear deformation effects. Numerical methods, such as the Finite Element Method (FEM), are necessary in practical applications as they are able to modelize general geometries, boundary conditions, loadings and materials. Among the significant

contributions in this field, Khatua et al [4] developed elements based on displacement fields, and Manwenya et al [5] published the formulation of a multilayer quadratic isoparametric plate element with layer-wise shear deformation theory involved. Ferreira [6] studied a three-layer sandwich plate, by considering the shear deformation effects of both skins and core. In the present paper, this latter work is briefly discussed.

2. THEORY

Modelling a layered structure like a sandwich plate, one frequently proceeds to a kind of homogenization to account for all the kinematic effects (membrane, bending, shear and interactions). However, this procedure does not capture completely the local effects of heterogeneous, highly non-symmetric sandwich structures. We propose a more accurate formulation which considers a three-layer plate (fig.1), each one of these can locally deform. The present approach considers the shear deformation effects in each layer.

The present shear deformation theory for general sandwich plates has been developed by assuming the displacement field in the following form:

In each layer, i , the middle-layer displacement field is found by

$$\{u_{i0}\} = \{u_{i0}, v_{i0}, w_i\}^T, \quad i=1,2,3 \quad (1)$$

in which u_{i0} , v_{i0} and w_i represents the i^{th} layer displacements about the x, y and z axes. For the first layer (top) we assume (by displacement continuity) that

$$\begin{aligned} u_{10} &= u_0 + \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{y2} + \frac{h_1}{2} \theta_{y1} \\ v_{10} &= v_0 - \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{x2} - \frac{h_1}{2} \theta_{x1} \\ w_1 &= w_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

in which h_i represents the i^{th} layer thickness and θ_{xi} , θ_{yi} the i^{th} layer rotations of the "normal" about the x and y axes. For layer 2 and 3 (core and bottom layer, respectively), expressions similar to (2) can be found. It is supposed that the laminate middle-surface is (conveniently) placed at core middle-surface. By this supposition we can write

$$\{u_{20}, v_{20}, w_{20}\}^T = \{u_0, v_0, w_0\}^T \quad (3)$$

The middle-surface displacement field of the 3rd layer (bottom) is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} u_{30} &= u_0 - \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{y2} - \frac{h_3}{2} \theta_{y3} \\ v_{30} &= v_0 + \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{x2} + \frac{h_3}{2} \theta_{x3} \\ w_3 &= w_0 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Fig.1 - Three-layer sandwich element - Geometry and displacement components

By setting z_i as a local i^{th} layer z coordinate as

$$-\frac{h_i}{2} \leq z_i \leq \frac{h_i}{2} \tag{5}$$

the i^{th} layer displacement field is found as

$$\{u_i\} = \{u_{i0}\} + z_i \{\theta_i\} \tag{6}$$

For the first layer (layer 1), for example, expression (6) can be developed as

$$\{u_1\} = \{u_{10}\} + z_1 \{\theta_1\} \tag{7}$$

or

$$\begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ v_1 \\ w_1 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 + \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{y2} + \frac{h_1}{2} \theta_{y1} \\ v_0 - \frac{h_2}{2} \theta_{x2} - \frac{h_1}{2} \theta_{x1} \\ w_0 \end{Bmatrix} + z_1 \begin{Bmatrix} \theta_{y1} \\ -\theta_{x1} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

For the other layers similar expressions can be found.

The strain - displacement relations for the i^{th} layer are as follows:

$$\left\{ \epsilon_{xi}, \epsilon_{yi}, \gamma_{xyi}, \gamma_{xzi}, \gamma_{yzi} \right\}^T = \left\{ \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial w_i}{\partial y} \right\}^T \quad (9)$$

In each layer, the strain tensor is divided into membrane $\{\epsilon^m\}_i$, bending $\{\epsilon^b\}_i$, shear $\{\epsilon^s\}_i$, and membrane-bending, $\{\epsilon^{mb}\}_i$:

$$\left\{ \epsilon \right\}_i = \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^m \\ \epsilon^s \\ \epsilon \end{Bmatrix}_i + \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^{mb} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}_i + z_i \begin{Bmatrix} \epsilon^b \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}_i \quad (10)$$

The membrane strains are constant through the sandwich thickness and are given for the i^{th} layer as:

$$\left\{ \epsilon^m \right\}_i = \left\{ \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \right\}^T \quad (11)$$

The bending strains are expressed by

$$\left\{ \epsilon^b \right\}_i = \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta_{yi}}{\partial x}, -\frac{\partial \theta_{xi}}{\partial y}, -\frac{\partial \theta_{xi}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \theta_{yi}}{\partial y} \right\}^T \quad (12)$$

The shear strains are given by

$$\left\{ \epsilon^s \right\}_i = \left\{ \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial x} + \theta_{yi}, \frac{\partial w_0}{\partial y} - \theta_{xi} \right\}^T \quad (13)$$

Finally, the membrane-bending strains for the top layer (layer 1) are expressed as

$$\left\{ \epsilon^{mb} \right\}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{h_1}{2} \frac{\partial \theta_{y1}}{\partial x} + \frac{h_2}{2} \frac{\partial \theta_{y2}}{\partial x} \\ -\frac{h_1}{2} \frac{\partial \theta_{x1}}{\partial y} - \frac{h_2}{2} \frac{\partial \theta_{x2}}{\partial y} \\ \frac{h_1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{y1}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \theta_{x1}}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{h_2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \theta_{y2}}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \theta_{x2}}{\partial x} \right) \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

The membrane-bending strains vanish for the core, as result of the sandwich middle-surface position. The expression for the bottom layer (layer 3) is similar to (14).

Notice that through this approach the membrane-bending effects are automatically achieved.

The material constitutive relations for the i^{th} layer can be written as $\{\sigma_i\} = [D_i] \{\epsilon_i\}$ or

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{13} \\ \tau_{23} \end{Bmatrix}_i = \begin{bmatrix} [D_1] & [0] \\ [0] & [D_2] \end{bmatrix}_i \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{23} \end{Bmatrix}_i \quad (15)$$

where $\{\sigma_i\}$ represents the stress tensor for the i^{th} layer referred to the layer coordinate axes (1,2,3), and $[D_i]$ is the reduced material stiffnesses matrix of the i^{th} layer and the following relations hold between these matrix coefficients and the engineering elastic constants:

$$[D_1]_i = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ \frac{\nu_{21}E_1}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & \frac{E_2}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{12} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (16)$$

$$[D_2]_i = \begin{bmatrix} G_{13} & 0 \\ 0 & G_{23} \end{bmatrix}_i \quad (17)$$

The stress-strain relation for the i^{th} layer in the laminate coordinate axes (x,y,z) are written as

$$\{\sigma'\}_i = [D']_i \{\varepsilon'\}_i \quad (18)$$

where

$$\{\sigma'\}_i^T = \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}_i \quad (19)$$

$$\{\varepsilon'\}_i^T = \{\varepsilon_x, \varepsilon_y, \gamma_{xy}, \gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz}\}_i \quad (20)$$

$$[D']_i = [\theta]_i^T [D]_i [\theta]_i \quad (21)$$

where $[\theta]_i$ represents the transformation matrix of the stress/strain vectors between the lamina and the laminate coordinate systems according to the usual transformation rule given in Jones[7]. Notice that in the present model no shear correction factors are applied to the shear elastic coefficients.

By integrating the stresses through the plate thickness, the generalized stress-resultant for the three-layer sandwich are obtained as:

$$\begin{aligned} \{N\} &= \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \{N_x, N_y, N_{xy}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{z_i^{\text{bot}}}^{z_i^{\text{top}}} \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}_i^T dz = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^3 \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}_i^T h_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 [D_1]_i \{[\varepsilon^m]_i + [\varepsilon^{mb}]_i\} h_i \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

The i^{th} -layer moments are calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \{M\} &= \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \{M_x, M_y, M_{xy}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{z_i^{\text{bot}}}^{z_i^{\text{top}}} \{\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \tau_{xy}\}_i^T z_i dz = \\ &= \int_{z_i^{\text{bot}}}^{z_i^{\text{top}}} [D_1]_i \{ \{\epsilon^m\}_i + \{\epsilon^{mb}\}_i + z_i \{\epsilon^b\}_i \} z_i dz = [D_1]_i \{\epsilon^b\}_i \frac{h_i^3}{12} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

(note that in this case $z_i^{\text{top}} = h_i/2$ and $z_i^{\text{bot}} = -h_i/2$)

The laminate moments are calculated by summing the latter (i^{th} -layer) moments produced by the i^{th} -layer position in z -direction. These latter moments are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \{\bar{M}\} &= \{\bar{M}_x, \bar{M}_y, \bar{M}_{xy}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \{\bar{M}_x, \bar{M}_y, \bar{M}_{xy}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{z_i^{\text{bot}}}^{z_i^{\text{top}}} [D_1]_i \{ \{\epsilon^m\}_i + \{\epsilon^{mb}\}_i \} z dz = \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^3 [D_1]_i \{ \{\epsilon^m\}_i + \{\epsilon^{mb}\}_i \} \frac{(z_i^{\text{top}})^2 - (z_i^{\text{bot}})^2}{2} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The laminate moments are then obtained as follows

$$\{M\} = \{\bar{M}\} + \sum_{i=1}^3 \{M\}_i = \sum_{i=1}^3 [D_1]_i \{ \{\epsilon^b\}_i \} \frac{h_i^3}{12} + [D_1]_i \{ \{\epsilon^m\}_i + \{\epsilon^{mb}\}_i \} \frac{(z_i^{\text{top}})^2 - (z_i^{\text{bot}})^2}{2} \quad (25)$$

The shear stress-resultants are expressed as

$$\{Q\} = \{Q_{xz}, Q_{yz}\}^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \{Q_{xz}, Q_{yz}\}_i^T = \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{z_i^{\text{bot}}}^{z_i^{\text{top}}} \{\tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}\}_i^T dz = \sum_{i=1}^3 [D_2]_i \{ \gamma_{xz}, \gamma_{yz} \}_i^T h_i \quad (26)$$

3. FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

In the standard finite element technique, the solution domain is discretized into n subdomains (elements) such that

$$\Pi(\delta) = \sum_{e=1}^n \Pi^e(\delta) \quad (27)$$

where Π and Π^e are the total potential energy of the system and the element, respectively. The element potential can be expressed in terms of the internal strain energy U^e and the external work done W^e for an element e as

$$\Pi^e(\delta) = U^e - W^e \quad (28)$$

in which $\{\delta\}$ is the vector of unknown displacement variables in the problem and is defined by

$$\{\delta\} = \{u_0, v_0, w_0, \theta_{x1}, \theta_{y1}, \theta_{x2}, \theta_{y2}, \theta_{x3}, \theta_{y3}\}^T \quad (29)$$

By assuming the same interpolation function to define all the components of the generalized displacement vector $\{\delta\}$, we can write

$$\{\delta\} = \sum_{i=1}^{NN} [N_i] \{\delta_i\} \quad (30)$$

in which NN is the number of nodes of the element, $[N_i]$ is the interpolating (shape) function matrix associated with node i and $\{\delta_i\}$ is the part of $\{\delta\}$ corresponding to node i.

The strain vector is related to the displacements vector as

$$\{\epsilon\} = [B] \{\delta\} \quad (31)$$

in which $[B]$ is the so-called strain-displacement matrix, containing the shape functions and their derivatives. The $[B]$ matrix is divided into membrane, bending, shear and membrane-bending matrices, according to the relations (30) and (9) to (15).

The elastic static stiffness matrix is achieved by the minimization of the internal strain energy [6] and is evaluated by summing up the contribution of the three layers as

$$K_{jk} = \sum_{i=1}^3 [K_{jk}]_i \quad (32)$$

or

$$\begin{aligned} K_{\bar{k}} = & \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^m]^T [D_1] [B_k^m]_i h_i \right] dA + \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^m]^T [D_1] [B_k^{mb}]_i h_i \right] dA + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^{mb}]^T [D_1] [B_k^m]_i h_i \right] dA + \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^{mb}]^T [D_1] [B_k^{mb}]_i h_i \right] dA + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \frac{h_i^3}{12} \left[[B_j^b]^T [D_1] [B_k^b]_i \right] dA + \sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{\Lambda} \left[[B_j^s]^T [D_2] [B_k^s]_i h_i \right] dA \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND DISCUSSION

A simply supported sandwich strip is analysed. The transversal applied load is expressed as

$$P = P_0 \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \quad (34)$$

The laminate is symmetric and has three layers, as illustrated in fig.2. The strip was discretized in six elements, in half of the length, due to symmetry considerations. Each layer is made of a unidirectional material, with the following nondimensional characteristics:

$$\frac{E_L}{E_T} = 25; \frac{G_{LT}}{E_T} = 0.5; \frac{G_{TT}}{E_T} = 0.2; \nu_{LT} = 0.2 \quad (35)$$

in which L and T represent, respectively, the longitudinal and transverse principal directions. The external layers are oriented in the x-direction, while the central layer is oriented in the y-direction.

Fig. 2 - Simply supported strip, under sinusoidal transversal loading, made of a three-layer cross-ply laminate

The variation of the central displacement with the a/h ratio, as well as bending and shear stress distributions, are compared in fig. 3, with the results of Figueiras [8], Srinivas [9], and the classical laminate plate theory. The results obtained suggest the following discussion:

- The application of the theory that supports the element formulation is correct for the solution of the present example;
- By comparing with other sources, in particular with the theory of Srinivas [9], the Serendipity element revealed excellent behaviour, specially in what concerns the normal and transverse shear stresses.
- The present example illustrates the shear deformation effects on thick plates behaviour, for which the classical laminate plate theory is inadequate for a/h ratios below 30.
- Through this formulation, without the use of any transverse shear correction factors, we are able to accurately predict, at each layer mid-surface, the transverse shear stresses.

Fig. 3 - Sandwich strip - a) Central displacement versus a/h ; b) Bending and transverse shear stresses

5. CONCLUSIONS

A very accurate model for sandwich plate finite element analysis is presented. This model is more accurate than the Mindlin first-order shear-deformation model [8] and much superior than Kirchhoff models. Both deflections and inplane stresses are precisely predicted, while transverse shear stresses are also predicted very precisely in each layer middle-surface. Shear correction factors, usually employed in first order shear deformation theories, like the Mindlin theory, are not used in the present approach.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The financial support of one of the authors (A.J.M.F.) by the Junta Nacional de Investigação Científica e Tecnológica through the project Programa Ciência BD/261/90-IC is gratefully acknowledged.

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